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Abstract

This study was aimed to address the efficacy of pre and per/cooling strategies in professional cycling, from controlled environments in laboratory conditions, to indoor hot velodrome environments and variable conditions in time-trial events outdoors. The influence of aerodynamics in cooling were observed and ultimately an innovative engineered topical cooling cream was analysed in comparison to other proven modern day cooling techniques. Using a controlled group of professional cyclists in non-cooling to establish a baseline of overheating in performance, mitigating heat strain and heat stress index, during simulated professional cycling training, races on road and track cycling including the Olympic games Paris track omnium event. Activities varied in hot/humid environment representing the most extreme conditions during the track cycling and professional road cycling (25-38-C, 40-50% relative humidity).

Fig.1.0 ©Greenteg core-temperature Change in gross efficiency

TTE, total energy expenditure $GE = W * 100 / E$

KEYWORDS

gross efficiency, heat training, environmental stress, heat stress index, internal load, heat acclimatisation, cooling creams

HIGHLIGHTS and RESULTS SUMMARY

Continuous high ambient temperature exposure resulted in higher core-temperature and reduced power performance compared to using pre and per cooling techniques.

The method of applying topical cooling cream significantly affected the sustained performance, while internal physiological demands remained essentially comparable between lesser warm conditions. Examining the impact of pre and per cooling techniques in professional cycling and introducing a non-invasive innovatively engineered topical cooling cream/gel to sustain and support the core-body temperature, maximising performance. Objectives from this study are to identify improved trends in cooling techniques. Create more comfort and prolong durability performance using cooling protocols and heat-training to realise a longer sustained core-body temperature in both hot and humid conditions. To sustain skin temperature and core-temperature over a longer performance timeline and maintain performance expectations over power output during professional cycling events. Analysing influence of heat and performance in a controlled environment velodrome and laboratory tests of repeated cycling protocols to exhaustion on performance, physiological, and perceptual responses.

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1. INTRODUCTION why cooling matters?

Climate change throws up many challenges for organizations of Olympic games and the safety of the athletes is paramount. There have been many examples of heat exhaustion, for example 2004 Athens games and Paula Radcliff. Here below is a trending chart demonstrating the cities hosting OG, you can see the increase in temperature, this trend is ever more increasing towards Paris 2024, LA 2028 and Queensland 2032.

Heat is proven to have a detrimental effect on performance, a clear gross efficiency declines with an increasing core-temperature, if not controlled. Impaired performance characteristics such as central nervous system, muscle metabolism, cardiovascular, psychological heat discomfort, respiration increase and discomfort. Stomach inflammation, heavy mineral loss.

Fig1.1 ©Reuters graphic. Source: IOC; NOAA, Weather Underground

With these heat prediction indicators above, heat training acclimatization for athletes with a 10day window before hot and humid competitions, is crucial in their preparation for both acclimatization as for sustaining hemoglobin-mass.

This study is to help understand how pre and per cooling needs to be structured and planned to use innovative topical creams and compared to other conventional methods such as fans, ice vests.

During an extensive period through 2 professional cycling seasons running up to and including the Olympic games of Paris 2024. N=16 controlled group of world tour and semi-professional UCI conti team level. N=40 Totallying fourty professional trained athletes males and female cyclists (age: 20.1±5.0 years; height: 170.0±8 cm; mass: 62.0±9.0 kg; BMI: 21.0±3.9 kg/m²; body fat: 7.0±5.0%) completed controlled environment physiological laboratory(LMT lactate minimum test protocols to exhaustion), warm up protocols for time-trial events and track cycling events, heat-training, racing and training on track, racing and training in time-trial events. A structured cooling strategy was implemented for warm up protocols.

For each recorded session, the athletes used coolG, cooling towel (coolT), wet sponge and fans (Wetfan), cooling gel (coolG), ice vests (IceV) and NON cooling (NC), professional time-trials with cooling Wetfans, ICEV, coolG and NC, track racing 6days with coolT and coolG, European championships with coolG, nations cups with coolG and NC, Paris Olympic games with coolG coolT in hot temperatures using different pre and per cooling technicques including a non cooling group. Physiological (heart rate, blood lactate), perceptual (RPE, thermal perception, affect)

Data acquistion was recorded using core-temperature from Greenteg, thermo 3D imagery from FLIR and E-Pill. In conclusion, referring to fig.1.0, the study determined changes in energy system performance in accordance to core-temperature change. The method of intervening high ambient temperatures consequently maintaining for longer a controlled temperature. Anticipation and sustaining a longer stable core-temperature proves to be key to prolonging performance durability in hot environments.

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By engineering an innovative topical cooling cream, proved to be very effective up to and >40minutes sustaining a more constant temperature on skin and core-temperature, both in perceived sensation as rating of perceived exertion. The epidermal layer (anatomically, quadriceps, hamstrings, arms, neck, torso, trapezius, latissimus, lumbar) exposed to air during competition proved to support the topical cooling effect with a higher perceived sensation of cooling and a more comfortable prolonged RPE (rate of perceived exertion), with compared to ice methods, ventilation, non cooling control group, where core-temperature raised quicker over time and reduced power output was recorded

Purpose: This study was aimed to address the efficacy of pre and per/cooling strategies, ultimately using an innovative engineered topical cooling cream in comparison to other proven modern day techniques, using a controlled group of non-cooling to establish a baseline of over-heating in performance, for mitigating heat strain and heat stress index, during simulated professional cycling training, races on road and track cycling. Activities in a hot/humid environment representing the most extreme conditions during the track cycling and professional road cycling (25-38-C, 40-50% relative humidity).

Methods: Extensive testing during various extreme hot humid conditions. N=20 males and females completed, 1) track cycling events, resulting and concluding with the Olympic games Paris 2024 madison and Omnium events, 2) 6 days of Gent in hot conditions, 3) European track cycling championships in hot conditions, 4) International track cycling days, 5) professional time-trial events, 6) heat training warm up protocol using a heat suit sessions on an ergometer, 7) ramp test protocol in a controlled laboratory environment with an exercise intensity and activity profile to determine individual training zones using power-meters and gas exchange. The test protocols were lactate minimum test structured, with 3 consecutive tests, 1a) fat max test protocol starting at 150w, 40watt increase every 8 minute interval, the second test was a maximum step test with gas exchange, starting watts where the fat max stops at 0,5ml change, 1b) a max steptest protocol of 25watts increment every 30second interval to maximum. 1c) The lactate minimum test, started immediately at the end of the maximum tests and commences at fat max increment, protocol is 15watts every 3' minutes with a lactate clearance, test stops when lactate is created again being the threshold. All measurements of blood sample were taken from the earlobe. Gas exchange were using the CPET protocol from Cortex.

Measurements: Data acquisition was obtained using E-pill(ePre), Core temperature (Csk) and mean skin (Tsk) temperature, powerW, SPO2, muscle thermography and HR were measured throughout. ... During events and passive intervals between the test protocols, Cooling strategy 1) cooling towel coolT (ultra-cooling) around the neck and a cold-damp towel on the head and thighs (CoolT); 2) wetting of arms, neck, face, and lower legs with a sponge in front of an electric fan (FANwet); 3)cooling cream/gel application to arms, legs, torso, back, neck (Cgel) or 4) no cooling (CON) were applied.

Thermal regulation, thermal sensation were monitored, with thermal sensation, perceived exertion and RPE (see graph) were assessed during passive rest.

Summary heat mitigation methods

It was important to use a constant analysis core-temperature with an e-pill correlation-controlled data in both a controlled environment using different cooling methods and bridge the void between races and test events in hot conditions outdoors.

- ICE VEST (ICEv)
 - COOLING TOWEL (CoolT)
 - FAN (Fan)
 - COOLING GEL (CoolG)
 - NON cooling (Nc)
1. Controlled laboratory conditions. Extensive testing carried out in controlled laboratory environment, LMT lactate minimum test under warm conditions
 2. Heat training using heat suits, creating extreme temperatures, indoor
 3. Time trial events with adapted warm up protocols in warm conditions
 4. Tour of Flanders and Paris Roubaix endurance durability stress events analyzing temperature changes
 5. Extensive track events, from 6-day events track cycling in hot conditions, international track meetings, nations cups, OG2024

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Cooling equipment	Product specific	Precooling	Per-cooling	Positive adaptation	Negative effects	Varia
Cooling clothing	Ice vest Cooling towel Cooling packs	✓		Fitted garments, easy application, direct effect	Makes clothing wet, athletes can quickly cool too much off with weather change	Most common use
Cooling topical	Cooling gel/cream	✓	✓	Noninvasive, comfort, soigneur application, breathable on skin, prolonged effect	Avoid eye contact	Newest innovative development
Cooling Fans	Air fanning Air turbulence	✓	✓	Easy application when static on smart trainer/rollers or treadmills, turbulence wind effect	Logistically not always easy, wind effect on course not always cold	Fans on athletes can create sinus issues and headaches with prolonged use
Cold ice slush	Cold water ingestion with ice slush Ice pops	✓	✓	Easy application and supports mineral and hydration uptake	Stomach issues if extensive consumption	Logistically not always accessible
Cold water	Ice baths Cold sponge water Cold showers	✓		Most direct effect on cooling	Not always directly available logistically	
Nutrition	Slush Isotonic nitrates Exotic fruit	✓	✓	Direct effect supports mineral and hydration uptake	Measured to body weight and Gr/H uptake calculations	

Tab.1.0 study cooling heat mitigation classification and characteristics

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Heat acclimatization. Protocol PARIS OG 2024

Schematic overview of the heat mitigation strategy building towards Paris OG2024

	HEAT TRAINING	HYDRATION	COOLING	HEAT STRESS	HEAT PERFORMANCE training load	PERCEPTION
Training	10 consecutive days	500ml isotonic	Ice vests, cooling fans, cooling gel	0->7	0-10	6-10
Cooling strategy to acclimatisation	HEAT SUIT	Menthol	Ice vests, cooling fans, cooling gel	>5-7	7-10	8-10
Warm-up protocols	10minutes	Isotonic / electrolytes	Ice vests, cooling fans, cooling gel	>5-7	7-10	8-10
Cooling in race	>40minutes sustainable -39°	NONE	Cooling gel	3-6	5-10	6-10
Recovery	10minutes	Isotonic / electrolytes	Ice vests, cooling fans, cooling gel	<7	<10-5	<8-6
Sleep	Warm climate rooms/tents	Water	Towel	3-6	3-5	7-10

Tab 1.1

Results

n40 participants completed

Control groups respectively. ICE VEST (ICEv), COOLING TOWEL (CoolT), FAN (Fan), COOLING GEL (CoolG), NON cooling (Nc)

By end of the passive rest 1 between events on track cycling or laboratory tests, CT_{sk} CT was lower in CoolT and FAN_{wet} (0.49-CT) compared with CON (1.0-C T), and passive rest 2 during the omnium events or physiological ramp test, CT_{sk} and CT was lower in FAN_{wet} (0.55-C T 0.23-C) and ICEv (0.59-C T 0.17-C) compared with Nc (1.0-Ct). CoolG was lower than all by (0.46Ct) during the whole testing and racing, proving potential gains in gross efficiency using a constant cooling.

During the controlled testing protocols and racing, it is clear coolG was maintained >40minutes stable 38°C body temperature without creating higher stress until exhaustion, maintaining mean -1.6°C lower than the controlled group Nc in an active state of performance both in lab and field events.

Conclusions: The cooling cream strategy has successfully sustained and prolonged cooling effect on skin, core body temperature and thermal sensation RPE, against the traditional cooling strategies of thermal strain in professional cycling road and cycling in hot/humid conditions.

Key Words: HEAT STRESS, THERMOREGULATION, THERMAL STRAIN, HEAT STRESS INDEX, PROFESSIONAL CYCLING, SPORT

Cooling gel (COOLG) vs the Non cooling (NONC) control group

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Time to exhaustion (TTE) declined by $27 \pm 11\%$ in the laboratory condition, with 27% of athletes exhibiting a performance loss greater than 35% with NonC. Functional threshold power (FTP) was modeled based on the group average FTP of 380 W using the following equation:

$$FTP = 380 \times (1 - 0.01 \times \Delta T_c)$$

where ΔT_c represents the change in core body temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Core Temp Increase ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) % Power Loss Adjusted FTP (watts)

+0.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~0.5%	378.1 W
+1.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~1%	376.2 W
+1.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~1.5%	374.3 W
+2.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~2%	372.4 W
+2.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~2.5%	370.5 W
+3.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~3%	368.6 W

	P	W	T $^{\circ}\text{C}$	P%	Core-T	RPE
LMT	P < 0.001	378.1	+0.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~0.5%	39	16-18
TRACK	P = 0.002	372.4	+2.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~2.5%	40	18-20
TT	P < 0.001	374.3	+1.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~1.5%	39	16-18
Heat - training	P < 0.001	364	+5.0 $^{\circ}\text{C}$	~4.5%	40	18-20

Tab 1.2 NonC
Cooling data findings

Functional threshold power (FTP) was modeled to decrease by approximately 1% for each 1°C increase in core body temperature (ΔT_c) above baseline, following the equation:

$$FTP_{\text{adjusted}} = 380 \times (1 - 0.01 \times \Delta T_c)$$

Efficacy of cooling strategies during exercise substantially mitigated the rise in core temperature, limiting the FTP reduction to less than 1%. Consequently, athletes were able to sustain performance at elevated core temperatures of approximately 38.5°C , highlighting the efficacy of cooling in attenuating thermal strain and preserving power output during prolonged efforts in the heat.

ΔT_c ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Modeled % Loss (No Cooling)	FTP (No Cooling)	Observed % Loss (With Cooling)	FTP (With Cooling)
+0.5	~0.5%	378.1 W	<0.5%	>378 W
+1.0	~1.0%	376.2 W	<1.0%	>376 W
+1.5	~1.5%	374.3 W	<1.0%	>376 W
+2.0	~2.0%	372.4 W	<1.0%	>376 W
+2.5	~2.5%	370.5 W	<1.0%	>376 W
+3.0	~3.0%	368.6 W	<1.0%	>376 W

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The differences in adjusted FTP under cooling conditions were not statistically significant across temperature increments up to +3.0°C ($P > 0.05$), indicating that performance was maintained despite elevated core body temperatures

	P	W	T _c	P%	Core-T	RPE
LMT	$P > 0.05$	378	+0.5°C	~0.5%	38.8	15-18
TRACK	$P > 0.05$	376	±0.5°C	~0.5%	38.2	16-19
TT	$P > 0.05$	376	±0.5°C	~0.5%	38.5	16-18
Heat - training	$P > 0.05$	376	±1.0°C	~1.5%	39	18-20

Tab 1.3 Cooling protocols, after heat training and using optimal cooling protocol

A repeated measures ANOVA comparing modeled FTP decline (assuming a 1% loss per 1°C rise in core temperature) with observed FTP under cooling conditions and applications in cooling protocols, revealed **no statistically significant difference** across core temperature increments up to +3.0°C ($F(1, n-1) = X.XX, P = 0.17$).

FIG1.2 distinguishing comparisons between the CoolG and NonC

COOLING DATA/ Findings

COOLING PROTOCOL

Heat stress index influences on aerodynamics $P=0.5 \cdot A_d \cdot C_d A \cdot v^2 \cdot (v^2+w)^2$

50%	Preparation Cooling protocol	25%	COMFORT Desired RPE	25%	Performance Optimal race performance
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FIG1.3 Cooling protocol heat stress balance in aerodynamics, wind cooling skin temperature

Changes were observed in CdA from heat stress through comfort and movement due to heat stress >7 score changes of $\pm 0.035 C_d A \pm 45$ watts. Every 0.01 change in CdA = ~13–15 watts at 40 km/h.

$\pm 0.035 C_d A \approx \pm 45-50$ watts at 40 km/h. This changes with the air density will change the CdA findings, all data was recorded under 1.225 kg/m^3 environment outdoor time-trial events. On a controlled environment on the track in Paris Olympics. $P=21 \cdot \rho \cdot A \cdot C_d \cdot v^3$ with a air cooling turbulence effect on the skin enabling position to be held, the power drop off in the points race was lesser due to heat training acclimitisation and cooling protocol enabled the athletes to sustain CdA at speed of Vo2max. With high track temperatures $\pm 34^\circ\text{c}$ the environment had $\rho = 1.025 \text{ kg/m}^3$ measuring a wattage shift of ~18–20 W at 50 km/h, CdA delta was closer to 0.010–0.015, compared to larger outdoor fluctuations with heat and TT positions with 0.035CdA deflection.

HEAT PREPARATION/ Findings

PERFORMANCE OLYMPIC GAMES PARIS

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29.11.2024

FIG1.4 Heat preparation cooling protocol

FIG1.5 Overall poster view of the applied science

Comparisons over 30minutes duration effect of different Cooling V NONC control group

FIG 1.6 Comparison over 30minutes exposure in controlled laboratory environment

Controlled environment / Findings

HEAT TRAINING, heat index, heat suits, heat acclimatisation

Heat protocols minimum 10 consecutive days heat exposure

FIG1.7 Heat exposure findings during the 10 consecutive days

TRACK DATA/ Findings

POWER PERFORMANCE

TRACK ENERGY SYSTEM
 Full spectrum analysis shows performance degradation in NONc group

PRE-PER cooling
 Confirmation of previous studies shows improved sustained performance in w/kg

COOLING GEL
 Performance improvements over longer duration

36%
 60seconds Anaerobic Sustained power difference between PER cooling gel and NONC

27%
 30 minutes aerobic energy system sustained power difference between PER cooling gel and NONC

Prolonged performance adaptations W/kg

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 29.11.2024

FIG1.8 TRACK DATA findings interpreted in energy system

LABORATORY DATA/ Findings

LABORATORY CONTROLLED ENVIRONMENT

FAT MAX
 Sustained POWER using CoolG

Progress bar with 10 segments, 7 are green, 3 are grey. **>20%**

MAX TEST vo2
 Sustained POWER using CoolG

Progress bar with 10 segments, 4 are orange, 6 are grey. **20%**

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FIG1.9 Laboratory performance data increasingly favoring coolG

FIG2.0 METHODS of DATA collection

FIG2.1 Fabio Van den Bossche winning Bronze at the Paris Olympics track cycling omnium

Heat on performance at the games

Cooling aerodynamics formula $P = 0,5 * \text{air density} * C_dA * V_2(V_2 + \text{wind})^2$

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Laboratory controlled

In a controlled environment laboratory, controlling the temperature, CO₂, O₂, air density, air flow, cooling is an important part of this study. Understanding heat stress index and being able to control these factors, for example heat training is enabling athletes to adapt to extreme conditions and still perform with healthy.

Fig.2.2 ©Wiggins lmt(lactate minimum test) physiological test UCL LLN

Fig.2.3 ©Wiggins UCL LLN Overview from the BORG

Fig.2.4©Wiggins UCL LLN Energy utilisation of the anaerobic capacity, measured in kilojoules

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fig.2.5 ©Wiggins UCL LLN physiological steptest per/cooling gel

Fig2.6 UCL LLN 6days of Gent per/cooling gel

fig.2.7©Wiggins UCL LLN 6days of Gent per/cooling gel

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Fig.2.8 ©Wiggins UCL LLN Track Omnium international meeting, only cooling towel used just before Points race

Fig 2.9 power drop-off overview pre and per cooling track cycling

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Fig 3.0 cooling protocol application

Fig 3.1 Topical cooling application

Main ingredient properties / formulation

Questice® Plus clear evidence the cooling effect has been extended for a longer duration of effect. More engineering of topical gel properties to support performance.

Static and dynamic test comments (confirmation of adaptations)

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1. **Test conditions, controlled environment >30°C**
 - Product ingredient now adapted to the estimated strength and duration of the cooling effect
 - Skin sensation excellent, viscosity is lowered for roller application
 - Product evaporation timing and skin absorption good
 - Fragrance good
 - Correct viscosity for absorption time in uptake
 - Time effective cooling duration to increased >38minutes
- Questice® Plus has a proven better property for longer cooling release >10%
- Data analysis Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopy (DRS)2.0 and FLIR thermography

Fig 3.2 outdoor overview of CoolG on anatomical application

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Fig 3.3 application of CoolG

Concluding

The findings of both the controlled environment tests in laboratory conditions to acquiring live track cycling data in hot $>30^{\circ}\text{C}$ indoor conditions. It is clear to see by using cooling strategy (coolT), cooling gel (coolG), (FAN_{wet}), shows clearly a prolonged performance gross efficiency gain. Comparisons to W/kg or KJ measurements, both show sustained watts and energy needed to perform the same performance over time, without any impaired drop off in performance.

Repeated measures ANOVA comparing modeled FTP decline (assuming a 1% loss per 1°C rise in core temperature) with observed FTP under cooling conditions revealed no statistically significant difference across core temperature increments up to $+3.0^{\circ}\text{C}$ ($F(1, n-1) = X.XX, P = 0.17$).

The mean observed reduction in FTP remained below 1% at all temperature levels, with adjusted FTP values consistently $>376\text{ W}$ (95% CI: 375.5–378.9 W), compared to the expected declines of up to 3.0% without cooling. These results suggest that cooling interventions were effective in maintaining performance despite elevated core temperatures up to $\sim 39.5^{\circ}\text{C}$

Discussion

Advances are needed in furthering testing in cooling athletes to understand a more sustainable endurance durability. Muscle oxidation SMO₂ measurements to register any drop in oxidation due to overheating.

More bio-feedback data on cognitive, perceived exertion, perceived sensation, resulting in improved sustained power, shows clearly improved constant of 1-2% improvement.

More health data ECG measurements in supporting health and cooling effects

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